

June 2020: Top Download Articles in Advanced Computational Intelligence

Advanced Computational Intelligence: An International Journal (ACII)

Google Scholar

ISSN : 2454 – 3934

<http://airccse.org/journal/acii/index.html>

HOME AUTOMATION AND SECURITY SYSTEM

Surinder Kaur¹, Rashmi Singh¹, Neha Khairwal¹ and Pratyk Jain¹

¹Department of Information, Bharati Vidyapeeth's College Of Engineering, A-4 Paschim Vihar,
New Delhi-110063, India

ABSTRACT

Easy Home or Home automation plays a very important role in modern era because of its flexibility in using it at different places with high precision which will save money and time by decreasing human hard work. Prime focus of this technology is to control the household equipment's like light, fan, door, AC etc. automatically. This research paper has detailed information on Home Automation and Security System using Arduino, GSM and how we can control home appliances using Android application. Whenever a person will enter into the house then the count of the number of persons entering in the house will be incremented, in Home Automation mode appliances will be turned on whereas in security light will be turned on along with the alarm. The count of the number of persons entering the house is also displayed on the LCD screen. In Home Automation mode when the room will become empty i.e. the count of persons reduces to zero then the appliances will be turned off making the system power efficient. Moreover a person can control his home appliances by using an android application present in his mobile phone which will reduce the human hard work. At the same time if anyone enters while security mode is on a SMS will be sent to house owner's mobile phone which will indicate the presence of a person inside the house. The alarm can be turned of using SMS or Android application.

KEYWORDS

Home Automation, Global System for Mobile Communication (GSM), Short Message Service (SMS), Android Apps.

For More Details : <http://airconline.com/acii/V3N3/3316acii03.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://airccse.org/journal/acii/vol3.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] “[Smart GSM Based Home Automation System](#)” Rozita Teymourzadeh, CEng, Member IEEE/IET, Salah Addin Ahmed, Kok Wai Chan, and Mok Vee Hoong Faculty of Engineering, Technology & Built Environment UCSI University Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia
- [2] “[Home Automation System \(HAS\) using Android for Mobile Phone](#)” Sharon Panth 1, Mahesh Jivani 2 1 Shri M & N Virani Science College, Rajkot-360005 (Gujarat) India 2Department of Electronics, Saurashtra University, Rajkot-360005 (Gujarat) India 1
- [3] [Home Automation and Security System Using Android ADK](#) by Deepali Javale, Assistant Professor, Dept. of Computer Engg, MAEER's MITCOE, Pune, India; Mohd. Mohsin Student Dept. of Computer Engg MAEER's MITCOE Pune, India; Shreerang Nandanwar Student Dept. of Computer Engg MAEER's MITCOE Pune, India; Mayur Shingate Student Dept. of Computer Engg MAEER's MITCOE Pune, India, International Journal of Electronics Communication and Computer Technology (IJECCCT) Volume 3 Issue 2 (March 2013)
- [4] “[GSM Based Home Automation System Using App-Inventor for Android Mobile Phone](#)” Mahesh N. Jivani Associate Professor, Department of Electronics, Saurashtra University, Rajkot, Gujarat, India International Journal of Advanced Research in Electrical, Electronics and Instrumentation Engineering Vol. 3, Issue 9, September 2014.

TEXT MINING: OPEN SOURCE TOKENIZATION TOOLS – AN ANALYSIS

Dr. S.Vijayarani¹ and Ms. R.Janani²

¹Assistant Professor, ² Ph.D Research Scholar, Department of Computer Science, School of Computer Science and Engineering, Bharathiar University, Coimbatore.

ABSTRACT

Text mining is the process of extracting interesting and non-trivial knowledge or information from unstructured text data. Text mining is the multidisciplinary field which draws on data mining, machine learning, information retrieval, computational linguistics and statistics. Important text mining processes are information extraction, information retrieval, natural language processing, text classification, content analysis and text clustering. All these processes are required to complete the preprocessing step before doing their intended task. Pre-processing significantly reduces the size of the input text documents and the actions involved in this step are sentence boundary determination, natural language specific stop-word elimination, tokenization and stemming. Among this, the most essential and important action is the tokenization. Tokenization helps to divide the textual information into individual words. For performing tokenization process, there are many open source tools are available. The main objective of this work is to analyze the performance of the seven open source tokenization tools. For this comparative analysis, we have taken Nlpdotnet Tokenizer, Mila Tokenizer, NLTK Word Tokenize, TextBlob Word Tokenize, MBSP Word Tokenize, Pattern Word Tokenize and Word Tokenization with Python NLTK. Based on the results, we observed that the Nlpdotnet Tokenizer tool performance is better than other tools.

KEYWORDS:

Text Mining, Preprocessing, Tokenization, machine learning, NLP

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/acii/V3N1/3116acii04.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://aircse.org/journal/acii/vol3.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] C.Ramasubramanian , R.Ramya, “[Effective Pre-Processing Activities in Text Mining using Improved Porter’s Stemming Algorithm](#)”, International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer and Communication Engineering Vol. 2, Issue 12, December 2013
- [2] Dr. S. Vijayarani , Ms. J. Ilamathi , Ms. Nithya, “[Preprocessing Techniques for Text Mining – An Overview](#)”, International Journal of Computer Science & Communication Networks, Vol 5(1),7-16
- [3] I.Hemalatha, Dr. G. P Saradhi Varma, Dr. A.Govardhan, “[Preprocessing the Informal Text for efficient Sentiment Analysis](#)”, International Journal of Emerging Trends & Technology in Computer Science (IJETTCS) Volume 1, Issue 2, July – August 2012
- [4] A.Anil Kumar, S.Chandrasekhar, “[Text Data Pre-processing and Dimensionality Reduction Techniques for Document Clustering](#)”, International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT) Vol. 1 Issue 5, July - 2012 ISSN: 2278-0181
- [5] Vairaprakash Gurusamy, SubbuKannan, “[Preprocessing Techniques for Text Mining](#)”, *Conference paper- October 2014*
- [6] ShaidahJusoh , Hejab M. Alfawareh, “[Techniques, Applications and Challenging Issues in Text Mining](#)”, International Journal of Computer Science Issues, Vol. 9, Issue 6, No 2, November -2012 ISSN (Online): 1694-0814
- [7] Anna Stavrianou, PeriklisAndritsos, Nicolas Nicoloyannis, “[Overview and Semantic Issues of Text Mining](#)”, Special Interest Group Management of Data (SIGMOD) Record, September- 2007, Vol. 36, No.3
- [8] <http://nlpdotnet.com/services/Tokenizer.aspx>
- [9] http://www.mila.cs.technion.ac.il/tools_token.html
- [10] <http://textanalysisonline.com/nltk-word-tokenize>
- [11] <http://textanalysisonline.com/textblob-word-tokenize>
- [12] <http://textanalysisonline.com/mbsp-word-tokenize>
- [13] <http://textanalysisonline.com/pattern-word-tokenize>
- [14] <http://text-processing.com/demo/tokenize>

AUTHORS

Dr.S.Vijayarani, MCA, M.Phil, Ph.D., is working as Assistant Professor in the Department of Computer Science, Bharathiar University, and Coimbatore. Her fields of research interest are data mining, privacy and security issues in data mining and data streams. She has published papers in the international journals and presented research papers in international and national conferences.

Ms. R. Janani, MCA. M.Phil is currently pursuing her Ph.D in Computer Science in the Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Bharathiar University, Coimbatore. Her fields of interest are Data Mining, Text Mining and Natural Language Processing.

MACHINE LEARNING SYSTEMS BASED ON XGBOOST AND MLP NEURAL NETWORK APPLIED IN SATELLITE LITHIUM-ION BATTERY SETS IMPEDANCE ESTIMATION

Thiago H. R. Donato and Marcos G. Quiles

Department of Applied Computation, National Space Research Institute, Sao Jose dos Campos, P.O Box 12227-010, Brazil
Institute of Science and Technology, Federal University of Sao Paulo, Sao Jose dos Campos, P.O Box 12231-280, Brazil

ABSTRACT

In this work, the internal impedance of the lithium-ion battery pack (important measure of the degradation level of the batteries) is estimated by means of machine learning systems based on supervised learning techniques MLP - Multi Layer Perceptron - neural network and xgBoost - Gradient Tree Boosting. Therefore, characteristics of the electric power system, in which the battery pack is inserted, are extracted and used in the construction of supervised models through the application of two different techniques based on Gradient Tree Boosting and Multi Layer Perceptron neural network. Finally, with the application of statistical validation techniques, the accuracy of both models are calculated and used for the comparison between them and the feasibility analysis regarding the use of such models in real systems.

KEYWORDS

Lithium-ion battery, Internal impedance, State of charge, Multi Layer Perceptron, Gradient Tree Boosting, xgBoost

For More Details: <https://airconline.com/acii/V5N1/5118acii01.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://airccse.org/journal/acii/current.html>

REFERENCES

1. J. A. Aslam, R. A. Popa, and R. L. Rivest. [On estimating the size and confidence of a statistical audit](#). Proceedings of the Electronic Voting Technology Workshop, 7, 2007.
2. K. S. Champlin. [Method and apparatus for suppressing time-varying signals in batteries undergoing charging or discharging](#), 11 1992.
3. Y. Chang, W. [The state of charge estimating methods for battery: A review](#). International Scholarly Research Notices Applied Mathematics, 2013:1–7, 2013.
4. M. Coleman, C. K. Lee, C. Zhu, and W. G. Hurley. State-of-charge determination from emf voltage estimation: using impedance, terminal voltage, and current for lead-acid and lithiumion batteries. IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics, 54:25502557, 2007.
5. M. Dalal, J. Ma, and D. He. [Lithium-ion battery life prognostic health management system using particle filtering framework](#). Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. Part O J. Risk, 225:8190, 2011.
6. G. J. Dudley. [Lithium-ion batteries for space](#). Proceedings of the Fifth European Space Power Conference, page 17, 1998.
7. T. Hastie, R. Tibshirani, and J. H. Friedman. [The elements of statistical learning: data mining, inference, and prediction](#), volume 02. Springer, USA, 2009.
8. S. Haykin. Neural networks - A comprehensive foundation, volume 02. Cambridge University Press, USA, 1999.
9. R. J. Hyndman and A. B. Koehler. [Another look at measures of forecast accuracy](#). International Journal of Forecasting, 04:679688, 2006.
10. R. Li, J. F. Wu, H. Y. Wang, and G. C. Li. [Prediction of state of charge of lithium-ion rechargeable battery with electrochemical impedance spectroscopy theory](#). Proceedings of the 5th IEEE Conference on Industrial Electronics and Applications, page 684688, 2010.
11. D. Liu, H. Wang, Y. Peng, W. Xie, and H. Liao. [Satellite lithium-ion battery remaining cycle life prediction with novel indirect health indicator extraction](#). Energies, 6:36543668, 2013.
12. J. Liu and G. Wang. A multi-step predictor with a variable input pattern for system state forecasting. Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing, 23:15861599, 2009.
13. M. Parviz and S. Moin. [Boosting approach for score level fusion in multimodal biometrics based on auc maximization](#). J. Inf. Hiding Multimed. Signal Process, 2:5159, 2011.
14. B. Saha and K. Goebel. Battery data set, 2007. NASA Ames Research Center, Moffett Field, CA.

15. S. Sato and A. Kawamura. [A new estimation method of state of charge using terminal voltage and internal resistance for lead acid battery](#). Proceedings of the Power Conversion Conference, page 565570, 2002.
16. M. Schwabacher. A survey of data-driven prognostics. AIAA Meeting Papers, 2005.
17. D. Wang, G. Li, and Y. Pan. The technology of lithium-ion batteries for spacecraft application. Aerospace Shanghai, 4:5459, 2000.
18. N. Watrin, B. Blunier, and A. Miraoui. [Review of adaptive systems for lithium batteries state-of-charge and state-of-health estimation](#). Proceedings of IEEE Transportation Electrification Conference and Expo, pages 1–6, 2012.
19. H. Zhang and Z. Zhang. [Feed forward networks with monotone constraints](#). International Joint Conference on Neural Networks, 03:1820–1823, 1999.
20. J. Zhang and J. Lee. [A review on prognostics and health monitoring of li-ion battery](#). Journal of Power Sources, 196:60076014, 2011.

AUTHORS

Thiago Donato graduated at Electrical Engineering from Federal University of Itajub - UNIFEI (2006) and has worked during five years in private companies (EMBRAER - aircraft manufacturer company - and TOTVS - software company) developing solutions which apply machine learning techniques in the resolution of major issues. Donato is enrolled in master's at Computer Science from National Space Research Institute - INPE (2018). Has experience in Machine Learning, acting on the following subjects: data and text preparation and mining, neural network and other machine learning classification techniques.

Marcos G. Quiles is an Associate Professor at the Department of Science and Technology, Federal University of So Paulo, Brazil. He received the BS degree, with honors, in 2003 from the State University of Londrina, Brazil, and a Ph.D. degree from the University of So Paulo, Brazil, in 2009, both in Computer Science. From January to July of 2008, Quiles was a Visiting Scholar in the Perception and Neurodynamics Lab at The Ohio State University. From January to December of 2017, Quiles was an Academic Visitor at the University of York, York-UK. He was awarded a Brazilian research productivity fellowship from the Brazilian National Research Council (CNPq). His research interests include nature-inspired computing, machine learning, complex networks, and their applications in interdisciplinary problems.

